

IMAGE SENSOR ABSOLUTE QUANTUM EFFICIENCY CHARACTERIZATION FOR RELIABLE PLANETARY GEOLOGY. A. Fsian^{1,2,3}, E. Robert¹, H. Dewitte² J.-B. Thomas³, N. Thret¹ and C. Virmondois¹
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Introduction: Multi Spectral Filter Array (MSFA) cameras are a key enabling technology for compact planetary exploration payloads. By integrating Fabry Perot interference filters directly onto a CMOS detector in repeating mosaic patterns, they enable single shot, co registered spatial and spectral acquisition without a mechanical filter wheel. Two such cameras, CAM-8 (an 8 band sensor with panchromatic pixels) and CAM-25 (a 25 band sensor), are being developed at CNES for the Rashid-3 lunar rover mission (MBRSC, launch no earlier than 2029) [1] (Fig. 1). The scientific objective is to discriminate geological signatures on the lunar surface from reflectance spectra in the 400 to 1000 nm range, targeting diagnostic absorption features of pyroxene, olivine, iron oxides, and volatiles [8].

Exploiting this spectral richness for quantitative geology requires that each pixel’s radiometric response be precisely known. The image processing chain under development, including demosaicing [2] and spectral analysis implemented in the CASPEX library [3], propagates whatever radiometric errors are present in the raw data directly into the reconstructed spectral cube. This paper addresses the upstream calibration step that makes all downstream science reliable: the empirical characterisation of the sensor’s Angular Quantum Efficiency, $QE(\lambda, \theta)$.

Fig. 1. CAM-8 mosaic pattern and spectral response curves of the 8 narrowband and PAN channels (wavelengths in nm).

Why Angular Calibration Matters: Fabry Perot filters are intrinsically angle sensitive. Their peak transmission wavelength shifts toward shorter wavelengths as the angle of incidence θ increases, following approximately $\lambda(\theta) = \lambda_{\perp} \cos\theta$. In any real camera with a finite aperture, rays spanning a range of Chief Ray Angles (CRA) illuminate the sensor simultaneously, so every acquired spectral band is a superposition of responses from different effective wavelengths. Manufacturing variances across a single chip can additionally cause peak wavelength to differ by up to 100 nm between pixels [4]. Standard manufacturer calibration files provide a single correction matrix at normal incidence and cannot compensate for this angular and spatial variability.

The consequences for geological interpretation are direct. A 10° mean off-axis angle induces a spectral shift of 5 to 15 nm [6]. For the $1 \mu\text{m}$ pyroxene band, this displaces the apparent absorption minimum outside the nominal channel and reduces retrieved band depth, biasing pyroxene to olivine abundance ratios. The blueshift moves the absorption feature toward shorter wavelengths and simultaneously narrows the effective FWHM, causing band depth to be underestimated. For hydration features near 950 nm, the blueshift moves spectral energy into an adjacent channel, producing a spurious absorption that could be misidentified as an independent geological signature. Without a rigorous characterisation of $QE(\lambda, \theta)$, these errors propagate silently through demosaicing and spectral reconstruction into the final science products (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Simulated Fabry Perot angular response at $\lambda = 645 \text{ nm}$. Each Gaussian curve represents a modelled spectral sensitivity profile $S(\theta)/S(0^\circ)$ vs. angle of incidence; the peak positions are derived from real measurements on the CAM-8 sensor. Peak blueshift and sensitivity roll-off increase with obliquity, reaching approximately 50% at $\pm 30^\circ$. Full per-pixel $QE(\lambda, \theta)$ characterisation results are in progress and will be reported in a forthcoming publication.

Calibration Protocol: We have developed an empirical metrological protocol at CEA-LETI to characterise $QE(\lambda, \theta)$ without relying on thin film optical models that may not represent the as manufactured sensor. The bench combines a double grating monochromator equipped with two filter wheels (400 to 700 nm and 700 to 1000 nm, $\Delta\lambda = 5 \text{ nm}$) with a motorised goniometer covering $\pm 30^\circ$ in 2° steps. Radiometric traceability is maintained via a NIST calibrated silicon photodiode on a flip stage placed at the sensor plane [5].

The protocol proceeds in two phases. Phase 1 establishes the absolute baseline $QE(\lambda, 0^\circ)$ at normal incidence by substituting the reference photodiode for the SFA sensor: the known photon flux $\Phi(\lambda)$ is derived from the measured beam power normalised to

pixel area and photon energy; the sensor signal in DN is converted to electrons via the Charge to Voltage Factor (CVF), i.e. the system conversion gain G ; and absolute QE follows from their ratio [5]. At each wavelength, 90 frames are acquired across 15 integration time steps spanning 1.5 ms to 700 ms (linear spacing) and averaged to suppress read noise. Phase 2 executes a full angular sweep, capturing raw frames at every (λ, θ) combination with simultaneous reference monitor recording to correct for source drift. The result is a per pixel Look Up Table (LUT) encoding both the spectral blueshift $\Delta\lambda(\theta)$ and the angular sensitivity roll off. For any mission optics characterised by a known CRA distribution, this LUT enables a rigorous per pixel correction before demosaicing and spectral inversion. It will be integrated into the CASPEX image processing library [3] as part of the Rashid-3 ground data processing pipeline.

Conclusion: MSFA cameras offer a compelling single shot spectral imaging solution for lunar rover missions. Their scientific value for geology depends critically on a calibration that goes beyond normal incidence QE: the angular response of each Fabry Perot channel must be empirically mapped and corrected. Without this, spectral band positions shift, band depths are underestimated, and the resulting geological identifications are unreliable. The empirical Angular QE protocol developed at CEA-LETI provides a NIST traceable, per pixel correction LUT that will be applied to the CAM-8 and CAM-25 sensors of Rashid-3 to ensure that spectral data products faithfully represent the composition of the lunar surface.

References: [1] Almatroushi H. et al. (2026) Rashid-3 mission: UAE's lunar rover to the South Pole, *ELS*. [2] Théret N. and Robert E. (2026) Demosaicing MSFA images: a high resolution spatial approach, *ELS*. [3] Théret N. et al. (2024) CASPEX Image Processing: a Tool for Space Exploration, *EPSC, Vol. 17*. [4] Hahn R. et al. (2020) *Opt. Eng.*, 59, 125102. [5] Gill A.S. et al. (2022) *Proc. SPIE*, 12191. [6] Dittrich P.G. et al. (2019) *Proc. SPIE*, 11144, 111440S. [7] Lapray P.J. et al. (2014) *Sensors*, 14, 21626 to 21659. [8] Flahaut J. et al. (2024) Candidate Landing Sites for the Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM) Rashid-1 Rover, *Space Sci. Rev.*, 220, 53.